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Optimization Of Facebook Usage For The Political Awareness Of Undergraduate Students In Federal Universities In The Southeast, Nigeria: Implications For 2027 General Elections

¹Akanwa Allwell Ononiwu; ²Azubiike Tochukwu & ³Mbamalu Nneoma

¹Lecturer III, Department of Computer Science
Federal Polytechnic, Nogodo-Isuochi, Abia State, Nigeria
Ao.akanwa@fpi.edu.ng
08032330317

²Special Assistant on Public Policy Formulation For Grassroot
Nwangele Local Government Area, Nigeria
Tochukwunma09@gmail.com
07065112609

³Higher Library Officer
Central Library
Federal Polytechnic, Nogodo-Isuochi, Abia State, Nigeria
Nneomaqueen50@gmail.com
08024495262

ABSTRACT

Facebook has become a costless and extremely effective tool in reaching mass audiences with political purposes in Nigeria, since it is the most popular social media platform in the country. The study examined the optimization of Facebook usage for the political awareness of undergraduate students in federal universities in the Southeast, Nigeria and its implications for 2027 general elections. The design employed for the study is descriptive survey. The population of the study comprised of the entire undergraduates in federal universities in Southeast, Nigeria. 306 undergraduate students were sampled using multistage sampling technique. Questionnaire was the major data collection tool. The data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation. While the null hypotheses was tested using t-test at 0.05 significance level. The results showed that, the major optimization of Facebook usage in political awareness of Undergraduate students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria are creating awareness of public policies among students, facilitate in dissemination of politically related information, and fosters exposure to political information. Gender does not significant influence the optimization of Facebook usage for political awareness of undergraduate students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria. However, gender has significant influence on the factors that affect the optimization of Facebook for the political awareness of undergraduate students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria. The study recommended that, more political awareness should be created among university students. Constant electric power should be provided around the university campus and even in students' lodges so that students can charge their devices.

Keywords: Facebook, Social Media, Undergraduate Students, Political Awareness, Political Purposes

INTRODUCTION

In the recent years, the social media penetration, most especially Facebook information production, dissemination and consumption have increased dramatically in Nigeria. This increase has affected politics in many ways. Facebook became a tool for politicians to carry out their political campaigns and for activists to create awareness on political issues and mobilize protests. Today almost in all political or social movements in Nigeria which include southeast the role of Facebook is being discussed. Facebook has become a costless and extremely effective tool in reaching mass audiences with political purposes in Nigeria, since it is the most popular social media platform in the country.

Facebook was founded by Mark Zuckerberg and launched in 2004. After 15 years of existence, Facebook has become, by far, the largest social network in the world (Ortiz-Ospina, 2019). Facebook like many other social media networking sites is a platform for communicating and interacting with family members, colleagues and friends around the globe (Mathew, Ogedebe & Ogedebe, 2016). According to Ronse (2019) Facebook is a popular social networking site that allows registered users to create profiles, upload photos and video, and send messages and keep in touch with friends, family and colleagues. Facebook is the most popular social media platform in Nigeria, as at September, 2021, Facebook has over 29 million active subscribers, out of which about 65% are between the age range of 16 and 34 years (Statista, 2021). This age range falls within the age bracket of university students. With this high percentage of students' age range on Facebook, information dissemination will be easy and faster and this might create awareness of the political system among the students. Facebook is certainly an effective way of delivering content and bringing awareness among general people (Reuter & Szakonyi, 2015). This implies that creating political awareness on Facebook is faster and less costly.

Political awareness can be explained as sensitivity to public policy and government. Delli, Carpini and Keeter (2014) defined political awareness as the range of factual information about politics that is stored in long-term memory. Political awareness is one's knowledge of political events, personalities, affairs, histories and institutions as measured by one's ability to provide correct answers to a specific set of fact-based questions. According to Zaller (2012) political awareness means the extent to which an individual pays attention to politics and understands what he or she has encountered. In other words, political awareness entails the intellectual or cognitive engagement with public affairs. Political awareness operates in the political information exchange between the individual and the various sources of political information communicated in the public space. Political awareness is regarded as important asset which determines participation and active citizenship in any democratic political system. Political awareness is extremely important for democracy, most especially developing democracy like Nigeria with high rate of voter's apathy. Without political awareness, citizens will not make informed decision about whom to vote for nor how well the government in power is performing, thus making them prone to accept political propaganda.

Studies have revealed that Nigerian university students have low political awareness and this affects their participation in politics. For instance, Rahman and Razali (2018) reported that University students have low political awareness which is the major factor affecting their active participation in political activities. When University students who are among the leaders of tomorrow possess low political awareness, they will be apolitical which can result to political apathy. Low political awareness generates superficial understanding of public policy, intolerance of minority groups and distrust of political institutions (Hart, et al., 2014). However, high political awareness produces politically informed, vigilant, vocal and competent citizens who have needed expertise for political participation to sustain functional and stable democratic system (Bennett & Freelon, 2012). Scholars perceive political awareness as the source of increased political participation which is effective for nations' development. It strengthens public awareness about government agenda that are driving politicians (Guo & Saxton, 2014). Certainly, Kleinnijenhuis, et al., (2015) reported that political awareness can be effective for the policy makers because it triggers the sense of public sensitivity which can strengthen the process of agenda development.

Political awareness among students is important in order to ensure they understand the political agenda and the problem of the nations. This is because the students are considered as the potential human capital in the future (Rahman & Razali, 2018). Similarly, Oluwatosin, et al, (2019) state that, youths and students are the largest bloc of voters in Nigeria but seemingly least politically informed. Thus, there is need to study the roles social media like Facebook can play in creating political awareness among students, most especially political science education students who are future political science teachers who will enlighten and impart the upcoming generation on the general awareness of the political system. Like any other social media platform, Facebook is expected to have much influence on students' political awareness which manifest in their informed political decision and active involvement in politics. Vitak (2011) proposed that there is a positive and direct relationship between the intensity in use of Facebook for political purposes and political participation among college students. Facebook makes youth and University students to bring together and accumulate political information and to advance their political efficacy. Vitak (2011) mentioned quite a few political activities that exist through typical features and functions of Facebook. These political actions are posting and placement of political status updates about politics, sharing the political messages with masses, scripting and distributing the political notes within their networks i.e. the party workers, getting comments from the public on their posts, sharing political opinions, joining political gathering via live streaming, following the contestants as well as downloading the political apps.

Gender can be defined as the socially constructed roles, behaviour, activities and attributes that a particular society considers for men and women (World Health Organization, WHO, 2014). To Woolfolk (2010) gender usually refers to traits and behaviours that a particular culture judges to be appropriate for men and women. Naturally, males are more interested in political issues than female. This interest might affect their level of awareness. On the other hand, females are more addicted to Facebook usage than male. According to David, et al., (2019) reported that females are more addicted to social media than male. on the contrary, Reuter (2019) reported that gender is not a significant predictor of social media use among students. This study seeks to examine the influence of gender on the role of Facebook usage in political awareness.

From the forgoing discussion, it is evident that Facebook is a great tool for dissemination of political information, if properly used among university students, since high political awareness is positively correlated with high political participation and involvement, the low political participation in southeast Nigeria as it manifests in low voters' turnout in recent general elections might be as a result of the level of political awareness of university students who are part of the major voters according to INEC records. Considering the fact that Facebook is the most popular and most subscribed social media platform in Nigeria which include southeast geopolitical zone. There is need to examine the roles that Facebook can play in the political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in Southeast, Nigeria where similar study has not been conducted to the best knowledge of the researchers.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to examine the optimization of Facebook usage for the political awareness of undergraduate students in federal universities in the Southeast, Nigeria and its implications for 2027 general elections The specific purposes of the study are:

1. Examine the optimization of Facebook usage in political awareness of Undergraduate students in Federal Universities in the South East, Nigeria.
2. Identify the factors that affect the optimization of Facebook for the political awareness of Undergraduate students in Federal Universities in the South East, Nigeria.
3. Find out the influence of gender on the optimization of Facebook usage for political awareness of Undergraduate students in Federal Universities in the South East, Nigeria.
4. Find out the influence of gender on the factors that affect the optimization of Facebook for the political awareness of Undergraduate students in Federal Universities in the South East, Nigeria.
5. Ascertain the implication of optimization of Facebook usage among university students for increased political awareness in the 2027 general elections.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study;

1. What are the optimization of Facebook usage in political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria?
2. What are the factors that affect the optimization of Facebook for the political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria?
3. What are the implications of the optimization of Facebook usage among university students for increased political awareness in the 2027 general elections?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses will guide the study and will be tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female university students on the optimization of Facebook usage in political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female university students on the factors that affect the optimization of Facebook for the political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria

LITERATURE REVIEW

Facebook is a social networking site which has the features of web 2.0 technologies to facilitate online information dissemination, interaction, uploading of pictures, videos, audios, text among others. Facebook ranks the second most used social media platform in Nigeria (Statisense, 2025). Among university students the website is an even more common stop than Google and outpaces MySpace by a significant margin (Anderson, 2017). More than 60% of members log in daily and many sign on multiple times a day while the average visitor spends over three hours of time on the site each month (Holahan, et al., 2017, Arrington 2015). The most common activities (based on time spent) overall are in descending order: browsing profiles, interacting with applications, browsing pictures, joining or visiting groups, searching for members and groups, and joining and browsing networks (Freiert, 2017).

Facebook fosters exposure to political awareness, mobilization and make political information more available, the medium is a potential means of recruiting people that were not politically motivated before into offline political activities (Abdu, et al., 2018). Thus, the accessibility and interactivity nature of Facebook can effectively function as what is now referred to as 'gateway participation' Nevertheless, studies have indicated that Facebook is more powerful than traditional media (Gromping, 2014). Facebook provides a similar and advanced features in terms of exposure to information but has the additional benefits and advantages of global reach, better quality and greater speed and also an interactive medium of online political discussion. With these features, Facebook shows a significant role in the formation of political awareness (Muntean, 2015).

Additionally, youth which include university students mostly get their political information from social media (Facebook) rather than the legacy traditional media such as radio, television and newspapers. The information given is more interactive, user friendly, concise and easier to comprehend. Youth are frequently posting political issues online, their views and opinions in relations to politics, sharing news and informative articles, their interaction with political actors and viewing videos about political activities (Lahabou & Wok, 2011). Therefore, it can be safe to say that Facebook is suitable medium to spread political awareness among youth and in turn increase their offline political participation.

University students select and use Facebook because it may satisfy their political information needs and desires, youth's social and psychological factors often mediate quality of information among them (Diemer & Li, 2011). Uses and Gratification theory for example has recently focused on motivational factors involved in social networks such as Facebook which shifted from simple information searching to active self-expression and participation in political activities (Tang & Lee, 2013). Thus, Facebook information quality is now becoming increasingly attractive predictor of participation into political affairs

as it provides accurate, complete, up to date, well arranged and organized information needed by the youth (Young & Quan-Haase, 2019).

Previous researches have documented that Facebook information quality can influence factors related to online political participation such as interactivity with individuals, usage intention to participate in offline political activities such as engaging in civic or community services (Ellen-Quintelier, 2017). This is because youth participation is often considered a significant element of a healthy democracy (Ellen-Quintelier & Vissers, 2018). It is imperative to note that university students use Facebook for many purposes, which include sourcing for political information which can in turn create political awareness among the students.

In an empirical study, Ali, Sohail and Hassan (2013) revealed that social media has an effect on the political awareness of students in University of Gujrat, Pakistan. The study also revealed that gender significantly affect the role of social media consumption on the political awareness of the students. In another study, Opeyemi (2018) reported that, online networking apparatus is normal particularly regarding drawing in political mindfulness among individuals. Social media is actively playing a role in strengthening political awareness of people. In addition, it can be further stated that social media trends can augment the awareness and engagement of citizens in political affairs. Similarly, Yunus (2013) revealed that, social media has already become a fundamental part of social movements and political awareness in Turkey.

An empirical study conducted by Muzaffar, et al., (2019) revealed that, social media plays a vital role in socializing and creating political awareness among Pakistani youths, precisely students of Bachelor of Science and Masters of Science Programmes Public Sectors universities in Gujranwala division. Muzaffar, et al. also found out that, Gender has no significant influence on the role of social in promoting political awareness among Bachelor of Science and Masters of Science Programmes Public Sectors universities in Gujranwala division. In another empirical study, Saroha (2016) found out that, young adults use social media platforms to a high extent for political information which improve their level of political awareness.

Another empirical study conducted by Oluwatosin, et al., (2019) revealed that, usage of social media had positive relationship with the level of political awareness of polytechnic undergraduates in polytechnic Ibadan, Nigeria. study by Abdu, et al., (2018) revealed that, Facebook use, interactivity with political figures, perceived Facebook information quality and political interest significantly correlates with youth offline political participation Given that new technologies have facilitated alternative forms of opinion expression and information consumption, more research is needed into the ways in which these technologies promote young adults' political participation. Another study conducted in Nigeria by Kurfi (2015) revealed that, social media, especially Facebook and twitter were used for creating political awareness during the 2015 Nigerian general elections. Facebook and Twitter have impacted on political awareness and communication and has provided a whole effective means for political mobilization. The study also revealed that, many used Facebook and twitter to campaign for their candidates others use the channel to spread political rumors. It was however found that political awareness and mobilization by Facebook and Twitter was limited to the people who had internet access or smart phones with internet applications.

Moreover, related empirical studies were also identified and reviewed. In the extant literature related to the study reviewed, it was observed that little effort has been made in investigating the role of Facebook usage on the political awareness of university students in universities who are the future of the country. Also, much of the available studies focused on social media generally. Considering the fact that Facebook is the largest social media platform and the most used social media platform among Nigeria based on report. It is imperative to examine the role it can play in enhancing the political awareness of university students. Thus, the present study seeks to fill in the gap by determining the role of Facebook usage on the political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the Southeast, Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Technological Determinism Theory propounded by Veblen (1929). The study is anchored on the interpretations of Technological Determinism which stated that media technology shapes how we as individuals in a society think, feel, act, and how society operates as we move from one technological age to another. This is to say that individuals learn and feel and think the way we do because of the messages we receive through the current technology that is available and which dominates communication in the society. In other words, the theory postulates that a society's technology determines the development of its political, social and cultural values. In relating the above to this study, Facebook, which is a media technology might have roles to play in the level of political awareness among university students by exposing them to political information online or through two-way communication with other users online. Thus, the findings of this study will either validate or refute the tenets of the Technological Determinism Theory.

Use and Gratification Theory (Blumler & Katz, 1974)

This study is also anchored on the Use and Gratification Theory propounded by Blumler and Katz (1974). Use and Gratification theory seeks to inquire into what effects, if any, the media might have on its audiences. The theory seeks to understand why people use certain types of media, what needs do they have to use the media, and what gratification do they get from the usage of such media. The theory assumes that the audience is active and its media use is goal oriented; media users are active rather than passive in seeking out media that meet their needs (Diddi & LaRose, 2006). People are rational and actively self-aware creatures that influence the effects media have on them and also unconsciously attempt to make sense of the media content in their own context. The theory also posits that users have alternate choices to satisfy their need, and their use or choice of a certain form of media. As a result, media users seek out a media source that best fulfills the needs of the users and gives them gratifications which are the expected outcomes, satisfaction or rewards of using a particular media form or program (Peirce, 2007). Similarly, Derek Lane suggests that media users play an active role in choosing and using the media. The theorist state that users take an active part in the communication process and are goal oriented in their media use. Use and gratifications theory posits that there are five groups of human needs which are specific in nature to the individual and how the media satisfies the need is subjective (Peirce, 2007).

In relating the tenets of this theory to this study, the role of Facebook as a type of media have on political awareness of university students is exemplified by the fact that social networks such as Facebook which shifted from simple information searching to active self-expression and participation in political activities could promote university students' political awareness or otherwise.

METHODOLOGY

The design employed for this study is descriptive survey. Descriptive survey is a research design that seeks a consensus of opinions of a representative sample population, about a general problem or situation which it should explain. This design according to Nworgu (2015) aims at collecting data on a particular research topic and describing in a systematic manner, the characteristics, features or facts about a given population. The descriptive survey was considered appropriate because this study seeks to collect, describe and summarize data on the optimization of Facebook usage on the political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria and its implications for the 2027 general elections. The study was carried out in South-East, Nigeria. The region is host to five (5) federal universities, one in each state of the federation. The choice of the area is being motivated by the fact that over the years there have been low political participation in south East, Nigeria as it manifests in low voter's turnout in South East, Nigeria when compared to Northern Nigeria.

The population of the study include undergraduate students in University of Nigeria Enugu State (UNN), Nnamdi Azikiwe University Anambra State (NAU), Federal University of Technology Owerri Imo state (FUTO), Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Abia State (MOUA), and Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu- Alike Ebonyi State (AE-FUNAI). The sample size of the study is 306 undergraduate

students in the federal universities in Southeast, Nigeria. Multistage sampling technique was employed in selecting the sample across the federal universities. A structured questionnaire titled: “Role of Facebook Usage on the Political Awareness of University Students Questionnaire” was developed by the researchers for the study. To ascertain the reliability of the questionnaire it was administered 20 copies of the instrument to 20 university students in Federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria, and it yielded a coefficient of 0.95 which indicates high reliability. The data collected for this research were analysed and presented using mean and standard deviation. To accept an item, its mean is equal to (=), or greater (>) than the criterion mean of 2.50, thus any mean less than 2.50 was rejected. While the null hypotheses were tested using t-test at 0.05 significance level. The null hypotheses were rejected when the P-value is less than the alpha value, but where the p-value is greater than the alpha value, the null hypotheses is accepted.

RESULTS

The presentation is done in tables based on the research questions and hypotheses that guided the study.

Research Question one: *What are the roles of Facebook usage in political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Mean rankings of respondents on the roles of Facebook usage in political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria

S/N	Facebook usage among students help to...	N	Mean	St.D	Decision
1	Create awareness of public policies among students	306	2.94	0.81	Accepted
2	Facilitate in dissemination of politically related information	306	3.50	0.74	Accepted
3	Facilitate online political participation among students	306	1.91	0.50	Rejected
4	Enhance students’ social engagement in the region	306	1.25	0.63	Rejected
5	Fosters exposure to political information	306	3.65	0.48	Accepted
6	Recruit people that were not politically motivated before into offline political activities	306	2.06	0.97	Rejected
7	Provides accurate, complete, up to date, well arranged and organized political information needed by the students	306	1.91	0.98	Rejected
Grand Mean			2.46	0.73	Rejected

The table above shows that roles of Facebook usage in political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria is poor. The roles of Facebook usage accepted among the students are creating awareness of public policies among students, facilitate in dissemination of politically related information, and fosters exposure to political information, with mean of 2.94, 3.50 and 3.65 respectively. While, other roles such as Facilitate online political participation among students, enhance students’ social engagement in the region, Recruit people that were not politically motivated before into offline political activities, and Provides accurate, complete, up to date, well arranged and organized political information needed by the students, with mean of 1.91, 1.25, 2.06 and 1.91 respectively were rejected among the respondents.

Research Question two: *What are the factors that affect the use of Facebook for the political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Mean rankings of respondents on the factors that affect the use of Facebook for the political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria

S/N	The use of Facebook among students are hindered by...	N	Mean	St.D	Decision
8	Inadequate internet connectivity	306	3.39	0.67	Accepted
9	Unstable electric power supply	306	3.65	0.57	Accepted
10	Lack of digital skills among political science students	306	3.70	0.46	Accepted
11	Technophobia among political science students	306	3.60	0.58	Accepted
12	Slow internet speed	306	3.59	0.81	Accepted
13	Lack of Interest in political information among the students	306	3.39	0.81	Accepted
14	Lack of trust on the political system among the students	306	3.29	0.96	Accepted
15	High cost of smart phone for using Facebook on the part of the students	306	3.39	0.81	Accepted
Grand Mean			3.50	0.71	Accepted

The table above shows that the major factors that affect the use of Facebook for the political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria are Lack of digital skills among political science students, Unstable electric power supply, Technophobia among political science students, and Slow internet speed, with mean of 3.70, 3.65, 3.60 and 3.59 respectively. Other factors are Inadequate internet connectivity, Lack of Interest in political information among the students, Lack of trust on the political system among the students, and High cost of smart phone for using Facebook on the part of the students, with 3.39, 3.39, 3.29 and 3.39 mean average respectively.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female university students on the role of Facebook usage in political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria.

Table 3: t-test analysis of mean ratings of male and female university students on the role of Facebook usage in political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria.

Gender	N	Mean	St. D	Df	t-cal	Sig	Decision
Male	112	2.07	0.96	304	0.172	0.864	Not significant
Female	194	2.05	0.99				

P<0.05

Table 3, shows that the t-test value 0.172 is significant at 0.864. Since the significant value of 0.864 is greater than 0.05 level of significance at which the null hypothesis is tested, the null hypothesis is therefore upheld. Hence, there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female university students on the role of Facebook usage in political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female university students on the factors that affect the use of Facebook for the political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria

Table 4: t-test analysis of mean ratings of male and female university students on the factors that affect the use of Facebook for the political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria

Gender	N	Mean	St. D	Df	t-cal	Sig	Decision
Male	112	3.53	0.61	304	2.698	0.007	Significant
Female	194	3.31	0.69				

P<0.05

Table 4, shows that the t-test value 2.698 is significant at 0.007. Since the significant value of 0.007 is less than 0.05 level of significance at which the null hypothesis is tested, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected. Hence, there was a significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female university students on the factors that affect the use of Facebook for the political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Optimization of Facebook Usage in Political Awareness of university Students in Federal Universities in the South East, Nigeria.

The findings of this study revealed that, the major optimization of Facebook usage in political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria are creating awareness of public policies among students, facilitate in dissemination of politically related information, and fosters exposure to political information. while, other roles such as facilitate online political participation among students, enhance students' social engagement in the region, recruit people that were not politically motivated before into offline political activities, and provides accurate, complete, up to date, well arranged and organized political information needed by the students were rejected. This is in accordance with that of Vitak (2011) who reported in his study that Facebook facilitates posting and placement of political status updates about politics, sharing the political messages with masses, scripting and distributing the political notes, getting comments from the public on their posts, sharing political opinions, but can hardly influence students to actively participate in practical politics as students affirms that they use it more for social communication than as a means of political engagement.

The study revealed that the role of Facebook usage in political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South East, Nigeria is low. The implications of this finding is that the Facebook usage has not significantly enhance the political awareness of political science education students.

Factors that Affect the optimization of Facebook for the Political Awareness of university Students in Federal Universities in the South East, Nigeria.

The findings of this study revealed that, the major factors that affect the optimization of Facebook for the political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria are Lack of digital skills among political science students, Unstable electric power supply, Technophobia among political science students, and Slow internet speed. This is in accordance with that of Hussain, Gulrez, and Tahirkheli (2012) who identified electricity failure, low bandwidth of the internet, lack of infrastructure like computers and laptops, poor time management during the semester, and health issues like backache, fingers/joint pain, dry face and blurred vision due to longer use of computer as the challenges associated with the utilization of social media among university students. Similarly, Adewoyin, Onuoha & Ikonne (2017) also identified unstable electric power supply, meagre internet access, and inadequate Information Communication Technology were some of the constrictions in the utilization of social media. poor internet connectivity, receiving of unwanted messages/pictures and electricity failure was considered as the leading problems encountered while using social media.

The study revealed that factors that affect the use of Facebook for the political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria are Lack of digital skills among political science students, Unstable electric power supply, Technophobia among political science students, and Slow internet speed. The implication of this finding is that many factors are affecting the use of Facebook for the political awareness of political science education students and if these factors are not resolved, Facebook usage will not improve the political awareness of students.

Influence of Gender on the optimization of Facebook Usage for Political Awareness of university Students in Federal Universities in the South East, Nigeria.

The findings of this study revealed that, gender does not significant influence the optimization of Facebook usage for political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria. This mean that being a male or female do not determine the role of Facebook Usage for Political Awareness of Political Science Education Students in Federal Universities in the South East, Nigeria.

This is contrary to that of Ali, Sohail & Hassan (2013) who found out that, gender significantly affect the role of social media consumption on the political awareness of the students.

The study revealed that gender does not significant influence the roles of Facebook usage for political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria. The implication of the findings is that any gender can use Facebook to enhance their political awareness.

Influence of Gender on the Factors that Affect the optimization of Facebook for the Political Awareness of university Students in Federal Universities in the South East, Nigeria

The findings of this study revealed that, gender has significant influence on the factors that affect the optimization of Facebook for the political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria. This mean that being a male or female determines the factors that affect the use of Facebook for the political awareness of political science education students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria. This is in accordance with that of Oluwatosin, Olusoji, Olusola and Olugbenga (2019) who earlier observed that gender has significant influence on the factors that affect the use of Facebook for the political awareness among youths in Nigeria.

The study revealed that gender has significant influence on the factors that affect the use of Facebook for the political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria. The implication of this finding is that, male and female students are affected by factors the use of Facebook for the political awareness of university students, however, male are more affected, thus more effort should be given to them.

CONCLUSION

The study examined the role of Facebook usage on the political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the Southeast, Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study concluded that, the major roles of Facebook usage in political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria are creating awareness of public policies among students, facilitate in dissemination of politically related information, and fosters exposure to political information. It was also concluded that, Facebook usage do not facilitate online political participation among students, enhance students' social engagement in the region, recruit people that were not politically motivated before into offline political activities, and provides accurate, complete, up to date, well arranged and organized political information needed by the students. The study also concluded that, the major factors that affect the use of Facebook for the political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria are lack of digital skills among political science students, unstable electric power supply, technophobia among political science students, and slow internet speed. Gender does not significant influence the roles of Facebook usage for political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria. However, gender has significant influence on the factors that affect the use of Facebook for the political awareness of university students in Federal Universities in the South-East, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Constant electric power should be provided around the university campus and even in students' lodges so that students can charge their devices
2. Data bundle subscription should be subsidized for students so that they can log in to Facebook at a very low cost.
3. More political awareness should be created among university students, who are expected to educate upcoming generation of political issues.

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